

NUMERICAL MODELLING OF PERFORATION RESISTANCE OF FOAM-BASED SANDWICH PANELS

J. Zhou¹, Z.W. Guan¹, W.J. Cantwell^{2*}

¹ Department of Engineering, University of Liverpool, Liverpool, L69 3GH, UK,

² Department of Aerospace Engineering, Khalifa University of Science, Technology and Research (KUSTAR), Abu Dhabi, UAE,

* Corresponding author (wesley.cantwell@kustar.ac.ae)

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Abstract

This paper describes the findings of a combined experimental/numerical study on the perforation resistance of sandwich structures. The impact response of sandwich panels based on PVC foam cores has been evaluated by determining the energy to perforate the panels. The dynamic response of the sandwich structures was predicted using the finite element analysis package Abaqus/Explicit. The validated FE models were used to study the impact response of sandwich panels subjected to pressure differential conditions, which includes sandwich panels supported on an aqueous support and equivalent to pressure difference at a flight altitude. The models were also used to investigate the effect of oblique loading.

Low velocity impact testing has shown that the energy to perforate the sandwich panels is dependent on the properties of the core. It is interesting to note that the 'wet' panels offer a lower resistance to perforation than their dry counterparts. It has been shown that sandwich panels impacted at high altitude offer a similar perforation resistance to those tested at sea level. Finally, it is evident that the perforation energy increases with impact angle.

1. Introduction

As a results of their excellent specific properties, composite sandwich structures are increasingly used in a wide range of lightweight structural roles, such as aerospace, maritime, and automotive components. A number of researchers have investigated the

response of sandwich structures to impact loading and much of this work has been summarised in detailed reviews on the topic [1]. Rejab et al [2] investigated the effect to the yield surface of rigid polyurethane foam by standard and multi-axial test using a special test rig. Reyes and Cantwell [3] carried out high velocity impact tests on sandwich panels based on fibre-metal laminate skins and an aluminium foam core and revealed that the introduction of metal layers into the composite skins increased the specific perforation energy of the sandwich panels by over twenty percent. Mines *et al* [4] studied the low velocity impact response of glass fibre/vinyl ester sandwich panels based on both aluminium honeycomb and Coremat cores and found that strain-rate effects increased the energy-absorbing capacity of the sandwich structures.

Few numerical studies have been undertaken to investigate the perforation behaviour of sandwich structures subjected to impact loading. Qiao et al [5] provide a brief overview for the research on impact mechanics and high-energy absorbing materials using different theoretical and computational methods. Zaera et al [6] have developed an analytical approach which based on the plate energy balance equation to simulate the dynamic response of metallic circular plates subjected to impulsive loads and the predictions validated by experimental results. Lee *et al* [7] developed a refined formulation of a composite sandwich panel to investigate the impact response of a sandwich plate. Aktay *et al* [8] used the finite element package PAM-CRASH to predict impact damage in sandwich panels based on

both PEI foam and Nomex honeycomb cores. Buitrago *et al.* [9], in their study, modeled the low velocity impact perforation response of lightweight sandwich structures based on a range of polymeric foams in various loading conditions.

Work presented in this study is to model the low velocity impact perforation response of lightweight sandwich structures based on a range of polymeric foams. Here, the finite element analysis package Abaqus/Explicit is developed to predict the response of the sandwich panels during impact by a steel projectile. Using validated models, the predictions response are modeled to investigate the sandwich panels tested in an aqueous environment, experienced flight altitude of an aircraft and a oblique loading condition that is difficult to conduct experimentally.

2. Experimental Study

2.1 Mode I and Mode II Test

Fig. 1 (a) Schematic of the SENB geometry and (b) schematic of the Mode II test geometry

In order to obtain the fracture energies in tension and in shear, both Mode I (opening) and Mode II (shear tests) tests on the foams have been carried for modeling development. Figure 1 shows the schematic of the single edge notch bending geometry (SENB) geometry and (b) schematic of the Mode II (shear tests) test geometry. The test results of load-displacement traces obtained following Mode I (opening) and Mode II tests on the foams have been calculated to the fracture energies in tension and in shear and summarized in Table 1 below. Damage development for FE models was controlled by fracture energies in tension and in shear.

Table 1. Work of fracture values and perforation energies of the sandwich structures.

Foam	Work of fracture in tension (kJ/m ²)	Work of fracture in shear (kJ/m ²)	E _{perforation} (J)
C60	0.26	6.48	10.69
C80	0.44	12.6	15.46
C130	0.76	27.6	27.06
L90	6.06	21.2	20.07
L140	12.1	27.3	25.56
PET105	2.3	7.38	9.12
PET135	2.5	18.2	19.03

2.2 Impact Test

Sandwich structures based on nine different types of polymer foams were manufactured by bonding with thin composite skins. Impact testing was conducted on 150 mm square panels using a drop-weight impact tower. The sandwich panels were impacted by a carriage with a 12.7 mm diameter hemispherical projectile. Here, the ring support used for the earlier perforation tests was filled with water for the perforation test supported on water. The impact force and indenter displacement were recorded using a piezoelectric load cell and a high speed video camera.

3. Finite Element Modeling

3.1 Modeling of GRRP

Numerical models were developed to model the dynamic response of the impact-loaded sandwich panels. Prior to damage initiation, GFRP was modelled as an orthotropic elastic material. The in-plane longitudinal and transverse moduli of elasticity were assumed to be equal since the GFRP skins were based on a plain weave. Damage initiation was modelled using Hashin’s failure criteria [10] which assume four damage initiation mechanisms, namely fibre tension, fibre compression, matrix tension and matrix compression. Using the longitudinal, transverse and shear effective stress tensor components within the plane of the GFRP, the damage initiation criteria can be determined [11]. Damage evolution is modelled by the negative slope of the equivalent stress-displacement relation after damage initiation is achieved. The fracture energies for fibre tension, fibre compression, matrix tension and matrix compression failure modes were specified to indicate the energy dissipated during damage development.

3.2 Modelling of PVC foam

The foam under compression was simulated as a crushable foam material for which the hardening curve was determined from a foam compression test. Deshpande and Fleck [12] proposed a phenomenological yield surface for these closed-cell foams as given by

$$\phi \equiv \frac{1}{\left[1 + \left(\frac{\alpha}{3}\right)^2\right]} \left[q^2 + \alpha^2 \sigma_m^2 \right] - \sigma_y^2 \leq 0 \tag{1}$$

where σ_y is the uniaxial tensile or compressive yield strength of the foam, q is the Von Mises stress, σ_m is the mean stress, α defines the shape

of the yield surface, which is related to the ratios of the initial uniaxial yield stress (σ_c^o) and the hydrostatic tensile yield stress (P_t) to the hydrostatic compressive yield stress (P_c^o), respectively. The yield stress (P_c) in hydrostatic compression provides the evolution of the yield surface size and can be expressed as:

$$P_c(\epsilon_{pl}^{vol}) = \frac{\sigma_c(\epsilon_{pl}^{vol}) \left[\sigma_c(\epsilon_{pl}^{vol}) \left(\frac{1}{\alpha^2} + \frac{1}{9} \right) + \frac{P_t}{3} \right]}{P_t + \frac{\sigma_c(\epsilon_{pl}^{vol})}{3}} \tag{2}$$

where ϵ_{pl}^{vol} is the plastic volumetric strain for the volumetric hardening model, which is equal to ϵ_{pl}^{axial} , uniaxial compressive plastic strain. Therefore, P_c should be determined from a uniaxial compression test on the foam. The rate-dependent hardening curves, in terms of the static relation, can be expressed as:

$$\bar{\sigma}(\bar{\epsilon}_{pl}, \dot{\bar{\epsilon}}_{pl}) = \sigma_y(\bar{\epsilon}_{pl}) R(\dot{\bar{\epsilon}}_{pl}) \tag{3}$$

where $\bar{\epsilon}_{pl}$ and R are the equivalent plastic strain and a stress ratio, respectively.

3.3 Resin Layers and Contact Conditions

The resin layers between the composite skins and the cores were modelled using cohesive elements [13]. The mechanisms of initiation and progression of damage were based on the maximum nominal stress and the effective displacement following a linear softening law. Damage initiation in the cohesive elements was evaluated using the ratios of the predicted nominal stress components, based on elastic traction-separation behaviour, to the corresponding critical values in tension (debonding)

or shear (sliding) at the interface, which can be represented as:

$$\max \left\{ \frac{t_n}{t_n^0}, \frac{t_s}{t_s^0}, \frac{t_t}{t_t^0} \right\} = 1 \quad (4)$$

where t_n , t_s and t_t are the stress components predicted by the elastic traction-separation behaviour for the current strain without damage and t_n^0 , t_s^0 and t_t^0 are the corresponding critical values of the nominal stress.

A surface-to-surface contact interaction was defined between the projectile surface and the node set of the target centre of the constituent layers of the sandwich to allow for finite sliding during perforation. The general contact interaction was included between the CFRP skin faces and foam cores to simulate the case where the cohesive layer is damaged by projectile. In addition, tie constraint were employed between all adjacent layers of sandwich to restore the interaction between each skin and the core layers.

Fig. 2. Geometrical, mesh, boundary and loading conditions of the sandwich model.

Modelling of the foam panel is carried out by removing the skins and cohesive layers in the sandwich panel. The cylindrical projectile has a mass of 5.56 kg which is assumed to be rigid in comparison to the sandwich panel. The foam was meshed by eight node reduced integration elements (C3D8R) and the skin by continuum shell elements (SC8R). Given that the panels were symmetric in nature, only a quarter of the panel was modelled here. Fig. 2 shows the geometrical, mesh, boundary and loading conditions of the sandwich panel.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Mode I and Mode II Test

Fig.3. Force-displacement curves from the single edge notch bending tests for different foam cores. (a. Crosslinked foams, b. Linear and PET foams).

Figures 3a and 3b show load-displacement traces obtained following Mode I opening test. An examination of Fig. 3a indicates that the crosslinked and PET foams fail in an unstable manner, whereas the linear PVC foam fails in a more ductile fashion involving gross plastic deformation in the cell walls. Failure in shear generally occurred in a stable fashion although some load drops were apparent in the crosslinked foams.

Fig. 4. Force-displacement curves from the shear tests for liner and PET foam cores. (a. Crosslinked foams, b. Linear and PET foams).

Fig. 4a and 4b show load-displacement traces of Mode II shear tests on the foams. The toughness properties of the foams were characterised by determining the work of fracture from the energy under the load-displacement traces and the area of the fractured ligament. The resulting values are presented in Table 1. Here, it is evident that the

Mode I fracture properties of the linear PVC foams are significantly higher than those associated with its crosslinked counterpart. It is also evident that the Mode II work of fracture properties of the foams much higher than the Mode I values, with the difference being most pronounced in the crosslinked systems.

Fig. 5. Perforation energy versus density for the linear PVC (circles) and crosslinked PVC (triangles) sandwich structures.

The energies required to perforate the PVC-based sandwich structures are shown in Fig. 5. Supplementary structures based on crosslinked PVC and linear foams were considered by extrapolating the mechanical properties of the initial foams given in Table 1. From the figure, it is also evident that the perforation resistance of the sandwich panel with the lowest density linear PVC core is superior to that of its crosslinked counterpart, whereas the converse is true for the higher density systems.

4.2 Impact Response in Aqueous Environment

The FE model predicted the response of a sandwich structure in an aqueous environment to reflect the case of a boat hull that is in collision with an immersed object.

Fig. 6 Comparison of load–displacement traces for the L140 core sandwich structures supported on water and on air.

An examination of the load-displacement traces of impact response of sandwich panels supported on water shown in Fig. 6, It indicates that the panels supported on the water foundation exhibit reasonably similar traces up to the point at which the projectile approaches the rear surface. Here, the force rises rapidly in the ‘wet’ system before dropping rapidly as the rear surface fractures. It is evidence that the rear surface peak is much higher in the fully-supported wet panel than in its dry counterpart.

Fig. 7. Comparison of energy absorption of sandwiches made with C130, PET135 and L140 foam cores between sandwiches supported on water and without support.

Fig. 7 shows the comparison of predicted and measured perforation energy absorption of sandwiches made with C130, PET135 and L140 foam cores between sandwiches supported on water and without support. It is interesting to note that the ‘wet’ panels offer a lower resistance to perforation than their dry counterparts. This reduction is largely associated with the inability of panel flexural deflection compare to the relatively flexible dry panel.

4.3 Air Pressure Differential at Altitude of Flight

In order to simulate the impact response of a sandwich structure subjected to a pressure difference between that of the cabin and that outside an aircraft at an altitude of 10000 metresl, the relationship between atmospheric pressure and altitude has to be employed. Here, the pressure is assumed to decrease in a nonlinear manner from the Earth’s surface to the top of the mesosphere. The pressure is affected by weather, temperature and relative humidity. Given that the temperature and relative humidity at sea level, the pressure within the troposphere can be calculated using:

$$p = p_0 \left(1 - \frac{L_T h}{T_0} \right)^{\frac{gM}{RT_0}} \approx p_0 \exp \left(-\frac{gMh}{RT_0} \right) \quad (5)$$

where p_0 is the atmospheric pressure at sea level; L_T is temperature lapse rate; T_0 is sea level standard temperature; $g = 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2$; M is molar mass of dry air; R is the universal gas constant, respectively. The above equation predicts that the atmosphere pressure at 10000 m is equivalent to 25691 Pa.

Fig. 8 Comparison of the predicted load-displacement traces of cross-linked foam sandwich structures at air-pressure difference.

Sandwich panels subjected to impact at an air-pressure difference between their front and rear faces was simulated to investigate the influence of impact in a differential pressure environment. Fig.8 shows the impact response of sandwich at pressure difference, solid lines for test results correspond to sea level conditions and the dashed lines for prediction correspond to conditions at 10000 m.

Fig. 9. Comparison of the predicted perforation resistances of a range of sandwich structures with no different pressure conditions between the front (impacted)face and the rear (non-impacted) face.

The predicted perforation energies for the sandwich structures subjected to an air-pressure differential with their corresponding samples without applying such environmental conditions has been compared and shown in Fig. 9. It is interesting to note that the panels subjected to the two different loading conditions offer similar resistances, suggesting that the perforation resistance of a sandwich structure at an altitude of 10,000 metres is similar to that at sea level.

4.4 The Effect of Obliquity on the Perforation Resistance

Normal impacts rarely occur in real engineering situations, components are more frequently perforated at some oblique angle. In the final part of this investigation, sandwich panels subjected to oblique impact has been predicted by the developed modeling.

Fig. 10 Load-displacement traces and cross sections of sandwich panels made with C130 cross-linked PVC and T105 PVC core subjected to oblique impact at incident angles of 10°, 20° and 30°.

In this investigation, the process of oblique impact on three types of sandwich structure was modelled and the load-displacement shown in Fig. 10. All

three traces exhibit similar trends with the rate of increase in perforation energy increasing with impact angle.

The variation of perforation with angle of obliquity for sandwich panels based on two crosslinked PVC cores and a PET foam has been predicted and shown in Fig. 11. Here, the impact angle refers to the angle between the axis of the projectile and the normal to the panel. From the figure, it is clear that the perforation energy increases with impact angle, for example, the PET105 passing from approximately 15 Joules for a normal impact to approximately 18 Joules for thirty degree loading. Interestingly, the increase in the perforation energy over this range of impact angles increases with foam toughness. Here, the PET105, C80 and C200 sandwich structures increase by approximately 18%, in passing from normal impact to a thirty degree impact.

Fig. 11. The variation of perforation energy with impact angle for three sandwich structures

Fig. 12 Geometric of elliptic oblique cylinder

A simple geometric analysis shows that the ratio of the surface area of an elliptic oblique cylinder to that of a right cylinder (the projectile creates an elliptical entrance hole on the top surface of the target) is given by:

$$2 \times \pi \times \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(r^2 + R^2)} \times \frac{h}{\cos(I)} - 2 \times \pi \times r \times h \quad (6)$$

Where r , h , R and I are as defined in Fig. 12. Similarly, the ratio of an elliptic oblique cylinder to that of a right cylinder is given by:

$$\pi \times r^2 \times \frac{h}{\cos(I)} - \pi \times r^2 \times h \quad (7)$$

Given that energy is dissipated in shearing both the composite and foam around the perimeter of the projectile as well as crushing the foam ahead of the impactor, the perforation energy will reflect a combination of both equations. Applying these expressions to the impact conditions at 30 degrees examined here indicates that the surface area increases by 24.8% and the volume by 15.5%. The average increase predicted by the finite element model was 18%, suggesting that the increase in perforation energy is associated with both the increased area of shear and the increased volume of material crushed under the impactor.

5. Conclusions

The impact response and perforation resistance of sandwich structures based on seven different types of foam has been characterised both experimentally and numerically. Agreement between the FE predictions and the experimental results was very good. It has been shown that sandwich structures impacted in a water environment offer a lower perforation resistance than those tested in air. The FE prediction show that sandwich structures impacted in an environment with an air-pressure difference offer a similar perforation resistance to those tested under normal atmospheric conditions. Final, it also present that the perforation energy of oblique impact increases with impact angle.

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